

Effective Parenting Models for Single Parent Mothers (Divorced)

Nur'aeni, N.¹, Kuntoro, K.²

¹Psychology, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

²Educational, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: *Single parent mothers have a role as breadwinners while educating and directing children so that children in the development process are in accordance with the expectations and ideals of being a child that is useful for family, society, and country, as well as religion. Therefore, mothers need to have an effective parenting model to achieve expectations and ideals. The aim of the study was to study and obtain effective parenting models from single parent mothers (divorced). The study was conducted with a qualitative approach to obtain a single parent's mothering profile, the willingness or expectation of a single parent mother to care for her child, weaknesses and strengths of parenting models that would be carried out by single parent mothers to their children and findings in the form of effective parenting models from single parent mothers. Data collection methods are documentation, questionnaires, interviews, observation and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Triangulation technique for collecting research data. Data analysis using interactive models. Activities in data analysis are data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The results of the study show that the parenting model used by single parent mothers includes models or patterns of democratic, authoritarian and permissive parenting, in accordance with aspects of child development.*

KEYWORDS –*Divorced, effective parenting, models, single parent*

I. INTRODUCTION

Marriage is an event, where a pair of brides or a pair of prospective husband and wife are formally met before the head of a particular religion or head, witnesses and a number of those present to be formally approved as husband and wife with certain ceremonies and rites. In Law Number 1 article 1 of 1974 concerning marriage, it is stated that marriage is an inner and outer bond between a man and a woman as a husband and wife with the aim of forming a happy and eternal family based on the One Godhead (Anonymous, 2007). A happy and lasting or eternal family is the hope and desire of all married couples, but hope is not always in accordance with reality. In married life there are times when problems occur that cannot be overcome and then cause divorce.

The divorce itself in general terms according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (<http://kamusbahasaIndonesia.org/2018>) is the separation of husband and wife so that they do not return intact in one marriage bond. Krantzer in Endah (2005) explained that divorce was the end of the relationship between two people who had lived together as husband and wife. Individuals who experience divorce will face many problems, including having to overcome their own situation, having to deal with children and explaining that their parents are divorced, and must face family and community problems. These problems can make an individual become depressed into a sad state. But in general, what women feel is more severe than men (Craig, 1992). The impact of this is that mothers become single parents in the care of their children.

Problems arise when divorced women must educate their children without the support of the father's figure for their child. Children often ask where is their father when they see their friends have complete parents. This was experienced by children from divorced women who had been informants in the study of Nur'aeni & Dwiyaniti

(2009) who asked about the existence of his father who had never returned home and his mother's confusion in educating and caring for her child without a father figure. Some even give up childcare to their housemaids (Dwiyanti & Nur'aeni, 2008).

The specific objectives achieved in this study are: **The research findings are effective parenting models from single parent mothers that can be applied.**

This research is very important in relation to efforts to empower women who become single parents because of divorce so that they can educate and care for their children effectively. The presence of a child for a family building is something that is very meaningful beyond anything so that in the daily social discourse it is often made at a light but meaningful conversation, that the ownership of children defeats luxury cars, terraced houses, large land and all kinds of material things.

In this regard, Dobos (Hidayah 2006) suggests that parents always look positively towards the existence of children. Philosophically for father and mother, children have important functions including: to show the immaturity of humans in the world, meaning that the existence of parents is not always there, but will be replaced by their children; expand the identity of the parents obtained through "breeding"; perpetuate family names with the achievements of their children; shows femininity and masculinity because parents have succeeded in having children; be the savior of the survival of marriage; the child will become a parent companion if one of them has died; and giving security, especially in a psychosocial perspective.

In line with this opinion, Sumapraja (Hidayah 2006) also expressed his opinion that in Indonesia children have value for their parents, namely: providing status of maturity and social identity; the child has the position of successor to the generation of his parents; by having children parents are given the opportunity to show their morality in the form of: sacrificial values, hard work, love, and care; all family decisions will consider the interests of the child; children become a means of showing the status of strength among parents, for example boasting of their achievements; children function as a place to depend on old days later.

This means that children are assets for parents in the family and more broadly are State assets, as stated by Supeno (2009), that the future of the State lies in children. In relation to this formally, the regulation on children in Indonesia has been very adequate. Aside from ratifying the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) which was approved by the United Nations (UN) in 1990, there are three laws concerning children, namely: 1) Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, 2) Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 3 of 1997 concerning Juvenile Courts, and 3) Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 4 of 1979 concerning Child Welfare (Anonim, t.t).

Regarding the Convention on the Rights of the Child, Dewi (1999) stated that in broad outline the convention which has 45 articles can be categorized into four major parts, namely: 1) the right to survival which includes the right to obtain the highest standard of health services. One of these rights is immunization against several diseases that cause death, 2) the right to protection, including the right to protection against discrimination, violence, neglect and exploitation. In addition, attention is also paid to the protection of children without families and children of refugees, 3) the right to develop, namely rights that cover all aspects of their lives, both physical, mental and socio-cultural aspects that must be adapted to the development of their age, 4) children's rights to participate, namely the right given to children to participate in their environment according to their perspective.

Seeing the importance of children's values for parents and the country, as well as the rights they have, has logical consequences for parents in the family to provide the best services in the development of psychology studies by serving the fulfillment of their developmental tasks to achieve the aspirations of competence. This was confirmed by Hurlock (1992), who argued that the failure of children in carrying out their development tasks, could cause children to experience behavioral problems, or problems in their adjustment so that they

could be said to be incompetent, because competent individuals are capable of utilizing environmental resources and personal to achieve good development results.

The importance of family for the development of children causes parents, especially mothers, to have a role in nurturing. Family is the main place of development and education for children. Santrock (2002) argues, that parents as the main figure for children, especially children who are still small (early childhood), ideally have time and energy, as well as dedication and commitment to nurture and educate their children, creating a basic concoction for children and provide learning experiences that are appropriate to the child's developmental stage.

Mothers and fathers play an important role in the development of positive attitudes or values towards behavior, emotions, cognition, education of life skills or independent learning, and a conducive environment that approaches competent early childhood education programs for their children. Andayani (2000) also argues, families in their function of educating children need to be the safest shelter for children when experiencing stress due to the socialization process, and must be able to provide social relationships called social relationships that are helpful by involving emotional aspects, information, all instruments and assessment assistance can be done by implementing effective care.

Garbarino & Been (Andayani & Kuncoro, 2004) said that parenting is a pattern of parental behavior accompanied by warmth, full of acceptance, understanding and giving appropriate responses to the needs of children. While Gunarsa (1995) said, parenting is a picture used by parents to care for children, namely caring for, caring for or educating. According to Dariyo (2004) quoting Baumrind's opinion, there are four types of child care including: 1) parenting with an authoritarian pattern, namely care that limits and requires children to follow parental orders without respecting the effort and results achieved by the child; 2) care with permissive patterns, namely care that does not have any demands (undermanding) to children; 3) care with neglect patterns, is a pattern of care that does not give attention to the child; and 4) parenting with an authoritative or democratic pattern, namely care that encourages children to be independent, but still sets limits and controls over their actions.

A. Definition of Parenting

Family is the place for the first time a child gets an education and knows values and rules which must be followed which underlies the child to conduct social relations with the wider environment. But with the differences in background, experience, education and interests of parents, there is a way to educate children.

According to Thoha (1996) who argued that parenting is the best way that can be taken in educating children as an embodiment of a sense of responsibility to children. The role of the family becomes important to educate children both in terms of religious reviews, social review and individual reviews. If family education can take place well then it can foster the development of a child's personality into an adult human who has a positive attitude towards religion, a strong and independent personality, physical and spiritual potential and intellectual that develop optimally.

From the description above, it can be concluded that parenting is a way of nurturing and the method of parental discipline in dealing with children with the aim of forming character, personality, and providing value for children to be able to adapt to the surrounding environment. In giving rules or values to their children each parent will provide a different form of care based on the parent's own parenting background so that it will produce a variety of different parenting from different parents.

B. Type of Parenting

Dariyo (2004) divides the form of parenting into four, namely a. Parenting with Authoritarian Patterns (parent oriented), characteristics of this care, emphasizing all the rules of the parents must be obeyed by the child. Parents act arbitrarily, without being able to be controlled by children. Children must obey and must not argue

with what the parents ordered. In this case, the child seems to be a "robot", so he lacks initiative, feels afraid of not being confident, anxious, inferior, insecure in association but on the other hand, children can rebel, be naughty, or escape reality, for example by use drugs. On the positive side, children who are educated in this upbringing tend to be disciplined namely obeying the rules.

Parenting with the Permissive (children centered) pattern, the nature of this upbringing, namely all family rules and provisions in the hands of children. What children do is allowed by parents. Parents obey all children's wishes. Children tend to act arbitrarily, without parental supervision. He is free to do whatever he wants. From another negative side, children are less disciplined with prevailing social rules. If the child is able to use the freedom responsibly, the child will become an independent, creative, initiative and able to realize his actualization.

Parenting with a democratic pattern, the position between parents and children is equal. A decision is taken together taking into account both parties. Children are given freedom of responsibility, meaning that what is done by children must still be under the supervision of parents and can be morally accountable. Parents and children cannot act arbitrarily. Children are trusted and trained to take responsibility for all their actions. The positive result of this upbringing, the child will become an individual who trusts others, is responsible for his actions, not hypocritical, honest. But the negative consequences, children will tend to undermine the authority of parental authority, if everything must be considered by children and parents.

Site care pattern, in this parenting style parents do not apply one type of parenting style. But the possibility of parents applying parenting in a flexible, flexible and adapted to the situation and conditions that took place at that time. According to Hurlock in Thoha (1996), there are three types of parenting styles for their children, namely:

1. Parenting with an Authoritarian pattern

Authoritarian parenting is characterized by ways of caring for children with strict rules, often forcing children to behave like themselves (parents), the freedom to act on their own behalf is limited. Children are rarely invited to communicate and exchange ideas with parents, parents assume that all their attitudes are correct so they do not need to be considered with children. Authoritarian parenting is also characterized by the use of harsh penalties, more use of corporal punishment, children are also regulated by all requirements with strict rules and are still enforced even though they have reached adulthood. Children who are raised in this kind of atmosphere will be big with the nature of being hesitant, weak in personality and unable to make decisions about anything.

2. Care with a democratic pattern.

Democratic parenting is characterized by parents' recognition of children's abilities, children are given the opportunity to not always depend on the parents. Parents give little freedom to children to choose what is best for themselves, children listen to their opinions, be involved intalks especially concerning the life of the child itself. Children are given the opportunity to develop their internal control so that they gradually practice to be accountable to themselves. Children are involved and given the opportunity to participate in managing their lives.

3. Care with a permissive pattern

This parenting style is characterized by the way parents educate children freely, children are considered as adults or young, he is given the widest allowance to do whatever he wants. Parental control of children is very weak, also does not provide significant guidance for their children. All what the child has done is true and does not need to get a warning, direction or guidance.

The opinions of experts on the form of parenting can be concluded that basically there are three patterns of parenting applied by parents, namely authoritarian parenting, democratic upbringing and free (permissive) parenting. Of the three forms of parenting, there is a tendency that democratic parenting is considered the best compared to other forms of parenting. However, in democratic parenting this is not perfect parenting, because after all there are things that are site-like as stated by Dariyo (2003), that no parent in caring for their children only uses one parenting style in educating and caring for their children. Thus, there is a tendency that there is no form of parenting that is purely applied by parents but parents can use the three forms of parenting according to the situation and conditions that occurred at that time.

In this study researchers refer to three forms of parenting, namely an authoritarian, democratic and permissive pattern. The three forms of parenting include educational activities in the family, the tendency of ways to educate children, ways to care for and how parents live. In the family, parents have a role in nurturing, guiding, and helping to direct children to become independent. Although the world of education also plays a role in providing opportunities for children to be independent, the family remains the pillar and first in shaping children to be independent. If the first and foremost parental education is unsuccessful, it can lead to less independent attitudes and behaviors in educating or caring for children.

Parenting according to Gunarsa (2003) consists of authoritarian parenting, democratic upbringing and permissive parenting. Parents who apply authoritarian parenting are parenting that emphasize the rules and boundaries that children must absolutely adhere to. Children must be obedient and submissive and there is no other choice that is in accordance with their own will or opinion. Parents rule and force without compromise, which results in children tend to have an attitude that is indifferent, passive, fearful, and easily anxious. Authoritarian ways lead to the loss of freedom in children, initiatives and activities become "blunt" in general, their personality is weak and so is their confidence. Parents who apply democratic upbringing are characterized by the attitude of parents who pay attention to and respect the freedom of children, but freedom that is not absolute and with understanding guidance between both parties, children and parents. In this democratic way the child grows a sense of responsibility to show something behavior and further fosters his confidence. He is able to act in accordance with the norms and freedoms that exist in him to obtain satisfaction and conformity and if his behavior is not pleasing to others he is able to delay and appreciate demands on his environment. Baldwin (in Gerungan, 1998) says that democratic education will make children become independent, not afraid and aim more in their lives.

Whereas if the child is educated by parents in a permissive manner, parents let the child search for and find their own procedures that give boundaries to behavior. Children are accustomed to managing and determining what they think is good. In general this condition is found in families that are too busy. Parents only act as "police" who oversee, reprimand, and may scold. Parents are not used to associating with children, relationships are not familiar and feel that children must know themselves. In children grow egoism (egocentrism) that is too strong and rigid and easy to cause difficulties if you have to deal with restrictions that exist in the social environment. In this upbringing, children are allowed to do whatever they want with a little restraint and fulfill the will of their children so that their children are happy so that they will not be independent.

Parents give little freedom to children to choose what is best for themselves, children listen to their opinions, be involved intalks especially concerning the life of the child itself. Children are given the opportunity to develop their internal control so that they gradually practice to be accountable to themselves. Children are involved and given the opportunity to participate in managing their lives.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

Subjects / Informants of this study were divorced and have children so they acted as single parents. There were 11 single parent mothers who became informants in this study. The data collection technique in this study is triangulation, which is a data collection technique that is combining various data collection techniques, which

includes data in the form of; In-depth interviews with informants, Focus Group Discussion and Questionnaire. The location of this study is at KUA Kembaran District. Data analysis was carried out at the time of data collection and after data collection was completed. Miles and Huberman (1984), activities in analyzing qualitative data are carried out interactively and take place continuously until complete, until the data is saturated. Activities in data analysis in this study are data reduction, data display and conclusion. A conclusion section must be included and should indicate clearly the advantages, limitations, and possible applications of the paper. Although a conclusion may review the main points of the paper, do not replicate the abstract as the conclusion. A conclusion might elaborate on the importance of the work or suggest applications and extentions.

III. RESEARCH RESULT

There is a picture of the weaknesses and strengths of parenting single parent mothers that are being carried out. Strengths of the Authoritarian parenting model: (1) The child becomes indifferent to his life, (2) The child becomes obedient, (3) The child is diligent in studying, (4) The child diligently recites the Qur'an, (5) The child obeys to the mother, (6) important to guide and educate young children, (7) Children are routine and do not forget to pray, while the weaknesses of the authoritarian parenting model: (1) Children are not diligent / lazy to learn, (2) Children cannot be responsible for what they do. Strengths of a democratic parenting model: (1) Can be applied to children and adolescents, (2) Children know the reasons for doing activities, (3) Children have an awareness of acting, (4) Foster a sense of responsibility, while weaknesses of the democratic parenting model: Mothers must explain all the reasons why an activity may be done or not. The strengths of the Permissive parenting model: (1) Children can explore according to their interests and talents, (2) Children are not depressed, while the weaknesses of the Permissive parenting model: Young children are not suitable because children need guidance and direction from their mothers.

Research findings in the form of effective parenting models from single parent mothers can be applied. There are 3 parenting methods used by mothers namely democratic, permissive and authoritarian parenting. There is a time when a mother uses three parenting patterns interchangeably, a mother does not only use one of the parenting patterns continuously when caring for her children.

The design of effective parenting models from single parent mothers (divorced) is adapted to several aspects namely;

1. The purpose of parenting

(a). Mothers can use a permissive care model as long as the child is happy by considering the impact that will occur if the care model is applied. (b). Mothers can use the authoritarian parenting model in determining the ideals of young children, so that children can be happy in the future. (c). Mothers can use democratic parenting when children ask why they have to do certain activities that are sometimes disliked by children or vice versa.

2. Educational aspects.

(a). Mothers can use a permissive parenting model when children choose and do their hobbies as in choosing extra-curricular activities. (b). Mother applies an authoritarian parenting model when teaching and giving examples of morals and religion. (c). The mother uses the democratic parenting model when directing children to choose and achieve their goals future.

3. The period of development

(a). Mothers use the authoritarian parenting model when children are children because they need and must be directed to the child's future success. (b). Mothers use the democratic parenting model when their teenagers are sometimes even permissive because they can already be responsible for what they do.

IV. CONCLUSION

The parenting model applied by single parent mothers to their children is largely a democratic parenting model / style even though there are those who apply authoritarian and permissive models. Democratic parenting model is an effective parenting model for single parent mothers to deliver their children to achieve their hopes and aspirations for the future. There are times when a mother uses three parenting patterns interchangeably, mothers don't just use one of the parenting patterns continuously when they care for their children.

The design of effective parenting models from single parent mothers (divorced) is adapted to several aspects namely; (1) Purpose of parenting, (2) Educational aspects, the model of care is adapted to aspects that will be instilled in children, for example for the moral aspects of the mother will apply an authoritarian parenting pattern, they will not tolerate children in terms of praying and studying unless the child is sick. (3) The period of development, mothers will apply an authoritarian parenting pattern to young children with the aim that children can achieve their goals in the future, while in adolescents, mothers will apply democratic parenting patterns.

V. Acknowledgements

Researchers would like to thank to Chancellor of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto University, Indonesia is Dr. Anjar Nugroho, M. Ag who has provided funding for this research.. Chairperson of the Institute for Research and Community Service is Dr. Suwarno, M. Si and Dean of the Faculty of Psychology, University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia is Retno Dwiyantri, S. Psi., M. Si.. Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Nur'aeni, departement of psychology, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

REFERENCES

- [1.] Astuti, R.D. 2006. Pengaruh Pola Asuh Orangtua Terhadap Kemandirian Siswa dalam Belajar pada Siswa Kelas Xi SMA Negeri Sumpiuh Kabupaten Banyumas Tahun Pelajaran 2005/2006. *Skripsi*. Diakses pada tanggal 22 Agustus 2010 dari <http://digilib.umnes.ac.id/gsd/collect/skripsi/index/assoc/HASH4d24.dir/doc.pdf>
- [2.] Baumrind, D. 1991. "The influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use". *Journal of Early Adolescence*, 11(1), 56-95.
- [3.] Dariyo, A. 2004. *Psikologi Perkembangan Remaja*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- [4.] Durkin, K. 1995. *Developmental Social Psychology*. 148-316. USA: Cambridge Publisher.
- [5.] Dwiyantri, R & Nur'aeni, N. 2008, *Analisis Kritis Tentang Perlindungan Psikososial Pembantu Rumah Tangga*, Laporan Penelitian
- [6.] Farid. 2009. Kasus Perceraian di Banyumas Meningkatkan Tajam. Diakses pada tanggal 20 Oktober dari 19 September 2010 dari <http://www.tempointeraktif.com/hg/nusa/2009/04/21/brk.2009042117-1619.id.html>
- [7.] Hurlock, E.B., 1992, *Psikologi Perkembangan, Suatu Pendekatan Sepanjang Rentang Kehidupan* (terjemah : Istiwardayanti dkk), Jakarta : Erlangga.
- [8.] Monks, FJ. Knoers. AMP dan Haditono SR. 1988. *Psikologi Perkembangan Pengantar dalam Berbagai Bagiannya*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- [9.] Nur'aeni, N., & Dwiyantri, R. 2009. DINAMIKA PSIKOLOGIS PEREMPUAN YANG BERCERAI (Studi Tentang Penyebab dan Status Janda Pada Kasus Perceraian di Purwokerto). *PSYCHO IDEA*, 7(1).
- [10.] Nur'aeni, N. & Dwiyantri, R, 2011, Self Monitoring Perempuan Yang Bercerai Terhadap penyesuaian Di Lingkungan, *Jurnal PsychoIdea*. Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto
- [11.] Suliswidiawati, Y. 2010. Bila Orangtua Bercerai. Diakses pada tanggal 20 September 2010 dari <http://bataviase.co.id/detailberita10524198.html>
- [12.] Taganing & Fortuna. 2008. Hubungan Pola Asuh Otoriter dengan Perilaku Agresif. *Skripsi*. (tidak diterbitkan). Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Gunadarma.
- [13.] Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang *Sistem Pendidikan Nasional*. 2003. Jakarta: Penerbit CV. Eka Jaya.
- [14.] Winarni, M. 2006. Dukungan Sosial Orangtua Kepada Anak dalam Belajar Ditinjau dari Tingkat Pendidikan Orangtua. *Makalah Seminar dalam Prosiding Seminar Nasional Isu-isu Kontemporer dalam Psikologi*. Yogyakarta: UAD Press.